

FEATURES OF ACCOUNT WORDS IN ADVERTISING TEXTS

Mamirova Dilnoza Shirinboyevna,
senior teacher of the Uzbek language
and literature department of the
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign
Languages, doctor of philosophy (PhD)
E-mail: mamirova.d@bk.ru

Annotation: The specifics of the number of word categories that perform an informative task in advertising texts are revealed in this article, and the advertiser's desire to have a pragmatic impact on a potential consumer is analyzed on the basis of examples.

Keywords: pragmatic impact, nouns, methodological characteristics, communicator, information, perception.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7299742>

Mamirova Dilnoza Shirinboyevna,
Samarqand davlat chet tillar instituti,
O'zbek tili va adabiyoti kafedrasida katta o'qituvchisi (PhD),
mamirova.d@bk.ru

Annotasiya: Reklama matnlarida informasion vazifa bajaradigan son so'z turkumlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ushbu maqolada ochib berilgan bo'lib, reklama beruvchi potensial iste'molchiga pragmatik ta'sir o'tkazishga intilishi misollar asosida tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: pragmatik ta'sir, ismlar, uslubiy xususiyat, kommunikator, axborot, idrok etish.

Мамирова Дильноза Ширинбоевна,
старший преподаватель кафедры узбекского языка и литературы,
доктор философских наук по филологическим наукам (PhD),
Самаркандский государственный институт иностранных языков
mamirova.d@bk.ru

Аннотация: В данной статье раскрывается специфика количества словесных категорий, выполняющих информативную задачу в рекламных текстах, и на основе примеров анализируется желание рекламодателя оказать прагматическое воздействие на потенциального потребителя.

Ключевые слова: прагматическое воздействие, существительные, методическая характеристика, коммуникатор, информация, восприятие.

Any advertising text provides information about advertised goods or services, manufacturers or suppliers. Therefore, the use of appropriate names is a tool that implements the information function (names of goods, manufacturers, trademarks, etc.). Almost any advertising text has corresponding names. D. Ye. Rosenthal explains the name "...a part of speech that combines words with the grammatical meaning of objectivity, which is expressed using independent categories of gender, number, Case, living and inanimate."¹ P.A. Lekant gives the following definition: "a noun is a part of speech that denotes an object and expresses the categorical meaning of objectivity in certain grammatical categories of living / inanimate, gender, number and case."² Thus, as part of speech, the names are known objects (sofa, shoe, ring), substances (acid, silver), living beings and organisms (lion, fly), real natural phenomena (snow, spring), abstract qualities and characteristics (delicacy, whiteness), actions and circumstances (work, step), place names (Samarkand, Bukhara), individuals (baby, child), etc. All names have an abstract grammatical meaning of objectivity.

One such name in advertising texts is the number Word category, which also has its own function and place. It is known that in the process of advertising, the advertiser seeks to have a pragmatic effect on the potential consumer, as a result of which the attitude of the other to the advertised object changes in a certain direction. "Most often, researchers of advertising texts do not pay due attention to the pragmatic features of the use of numbers used in the text, taking into account the lexical, syntactic and methodological features of the advertising text."³ Some researchers believe that numbers are mainly used as an information address in the information part of the advertising text, indicating the exact address of the firm or store: "Estaya Street 58,. Tel. 32-87-91", "jewelry salons 50-World Gold", " Insurance Center – st. 1, 14 may, tel. Prices in the Metro store "55-87-50": chicken 1 kg – 470 coins, buckwheat 800 g-285 coins". But since language is a product of the process of thinking, perception, it also reflects the quantitative characteristics of reality. It is necessary to consider the word category as an integral element of the text of modern advertising, since the numbers attract the addressee and enhance the impact of advertising on consumers, while talking about social life vagaries, the numbers express the text more clearly than the facts: chocolate paste number one in Uzbekistan Chococream – a selection of millions.

Hence, the main purpose of the numbers used in advertising texts is to reflect objective and impartial information. At the same time, when carrying out the interpretation of background information of communicators (their feelings, views, relationships, value orientations, etc.) in social communication, numbers in a certain context serve as a source of speech expression: the Samsung Galaxy S7 will be able to get full power in 30 minutes.

The frequency with which the number Word series is used (as in the table presented above) is a very small percentage of all lexical units in the advertising text. "Because

¹ <http://hi-edu.ru/e-books/xbook107/01/about.htm>. Валгина Н.С., Розенталь Д.Э., Фомина М.И. Современный русский язык: Учебник / Под редакцией Н.С. Валгиной. - 6-е изд. – Москва: Логос, 2002. – 528 с.

² Лекант П.А., Гольцова Н.Г., Жуков В.П. и др. Современный русский литературный язык: Учебник/ Под ред. П.А. Леканта. – 5-е изд. – Москва: Высшая школа, 2001. – С.195.

³ <http://articlekz.com/article/13381/> Филиппова Д.Н., Антонова Н. [Лексикология. Реклама. Художественный текст](#). Журнал: [Вестник Инновационного Евразийского университета](#). – Павлодар, 2012.

oversaturation of a text with facts carried out using numbers makes the reader tired."⁴ Words belonging to the number category are used to express quantitative values, number, indicate a place in the number line. For example, in social ads, the number can also be approximate: to date, about 15 thousand people have died from this disease. In the cited text there is an abstraction, although the number is used, it shows not the exact amount, but the assumption. Advertising quoted in the language of traders should show with proof of quantity quoted, not assumptions: Best moments cough cause do not get out of hand, Lozalvan – three-way effect against cough: dilutes phlegm, cleanses the respiratory tract and protects the lungs. Lazolvan – the best times are with you. As proof of the three-way ni in this example: liquefies phlegm, cleanses the airways and protects the lungs vs is cited as evidence. An advertising message should stand out in the flow of messages of the same type, so very often the quantitative aspect of this information is taken into account.

The use of numbers helps in achieving the marketing goals of the reader and advertiser on information using numbers associated with the desire of the author to provide objective and reliable information, to attract attention in the advertising text.

In place of the conclusion, it can be said that abstract names used in advertising texts make it possible to characterize various situations, objects and phenomena. The most beautiful part of speech is the numbers used in advertising texts. Performs an informative task in advertising texts. Although verbs, adjectives, pronouns in the language of adverbs are also used, but serve as a bright source of expression.

REFERENCES

1. <http://hi-edu.ru/e-books/xbook107/01/about.htm>. Valgina N.S., Rozental D.E., Fomina M.I. *Sovremennyy russkiy yazyk: Uchebnik / Pod redaksiyey N.S. Valginoy*. - 6-ye izd. – Moskva: Logos, 2002. – 528 s.
2. Lekant P.A., Golsova N.G., Jukov V.P. i dr. *Sovremennyy russkiy literaturnyy yazyk: Uchebnik/ Pod red. P.A. Lekanta*. – 5-ye izd. – Moskva: Vysshaya shkola, 2001. – S.195.
3. <http://articlekz.com/article/13381/> Filippova D.N., Antonova N. *Leksikologiya. Reklama. Xudojestvennyy tekst*. Jurnal: *Vestnik Innovatsionnogo Yevraziyskogo universiteta*. – *Pavlodar*, 2012.
4. Kara Murza Ye.S. *Prepodavaniye i izucheniye russkoy kommercheskoy reklamy v mediavuze // Medialingvistika*. 2018. T. 5. № 1. – S. 97-109.
5. Мамирова, Д. Ш. (2020). *REKLAMA MATNLARINING TIL XUSUSIYATLARI. МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 3(4).
6. Мамирова, Д. (2018). *Реклама матнларининг ўзига хос хусусиятлари ҳақида айрим мулоҳазалар. Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование*, 3(3 (68)), 56-59.

⁴ Кара Мурза Е.С. *Преподавание и изучение русской коммерческой рекламы в медиавузе // Медиалингвистика*. 2018. Т. 5. № 1. – С. 97-109.

7. SHIRINBOYEVNA, M. D. Basic Features Of Advertising Language. *JournalNX*, 6(10), 325-330.
8. Холова, М. (2015). МАСТЕРСТВО СОЗДАНИЯ ПОЭТИЧЕСКИХ СИМВОЛОВ В ЛИРИКЕ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ПОЭЗИИ ФАХРИЁРА). In *Современная филология: теория и практика* (pp. 114-119).
9. Холова, М. (2019). Рауф парфи шеърлари бадиияти. *Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование*, 4(1 (70)), 67-70.
10. Пардаева, И. (2018). Анушервон адолат тимсоли. *Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование*, 3(2 (67)), 109-112.
11. Matayunusovna, P. I. (2021). "BOBURNOMA" AS A HISTORICAL AND LITERARY SOURCE. *Thematics Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(5).
12. Рахматова, Д. (2021). Сайқалланаётган "Ўткан кунлар". *Общество и инновации*, 2(3/S), 173-179.
13. Rakhmatova, D. (2020). MAKHMUDKHUJA BEKHBUDI AND LANGUAGE ISSUE. *Интернаука*, 24(153 часть 3), 11.
14. Nusratilloevna, R. D. (2020). Makhmudkhuja Bekhbudi and Enlightenment. *Проблемы науки*, (6 (54)), 60-62.